

GROWTH AND REPRODUCTION CHARACTERISTICS OF BLACK FISH (*SCHIZOTHORAX INTERMEDIUS*) IN A PASTORAL POOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14023660>

Abstract. The given article discusses about black fish (*Schizothorax intermedius*) of Chervok reservoir, is engaged in increasing the concentration of its consumption and medicinal properties by acclimatization to the conditions of habitat in nature. New scientific projects are presented based on a thorough study of the functions of the anus and the base of the anal fin of these fish by domesticating the living conditions of black fish, observing the coefficient of variability and comparing the processes of flight to them in natural conditions. In addition, it consists in analyzing the condition of the fish, from class to meat concentration, depending on changes in the scales of black fish.

Keywords: yingachal, brachial fin, anal fin, aquatic plants, chronimid larvae, schizothorax, intermediate, oscillating, collector, temperature, Chugunov method, annular center in a strap.

It is important to suggest that morphological characteristics of 19 out of 32 fish samples collected from the Chervok Reservoir in September and October are close to those of carp species. The the book "Neighboring Districts Fish Detector" published in Tashkent in 2011 was used [4, 5]. *Schizothorax intermedius* is described in the definition as follows. The mouth is lower or half lower. The coins are small. The anus and the base of the anal fin are covered with a row of widened setae. The abdomen is black. The number of spines III-IV on the brachial fin is 7-9, on the anal fin III - 5. There are about 85-122 coins on the lateral line. The body length is up to 45 cm, the weight is up to 1.5 kg. It is widely distributed in Uzbekistan, found mainly in foothill and mountain rivers, as well as in canals, collectors and some springs. It reaches sexual maturity at the age of 2-3 years. The spawning period is from April to August, the stone-gravel sections of the river are flooded. Its density consists of 5-50 thousand cells. It feeds on aquatic plants, springtails and chronimid larvae, insects [10].

Definitely, black fish (*Schizothorax intermedius*) was found in the Chervok reservoir. The structure of the mouth of the fish caught from the reservoir, the number of scales, the number of gills and other features are very close to the features displayed in the detector. In the herd of black fish, along with females and males, there are also fry. 19 carp were delivered to the sample and their measurements were made. Thrushes grow slowly. Males reach sexual maturity at 2-3 years, females - at 3-4 years (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Age determination of blackfish (*Schizothorax intermedius*) in Chervok Reservoir.

Figure 2. Specimens of blackfish (*Schizothoraxintermedius*).

Samples of blackfish (*Schizothoraxintermedius*) were taken from the tail of blackfish (*Schizothoraxintermedius*) (04/27/2021) at the Institute of Zoology of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Based on the materials brought from Chervok Reservoir, samples of the hind fins of blackfish (*Schizothoraxintermedius*) were taken at the Institute of Zoology of the Russian Academy of Sciences (04/27/2021) and the results were analyzed [2-3]. In the laboratory of the Institute of Zoology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 19 samples of carp brought from the Chervok Reservoir were examined. The sizes of the samples (length of the whole fish, length without tail and weight) were measured using special equipment. To determine the age of the fish, samples were taken from them and a preparation was made. The age of the fish was determined by the number of rings on the scales [6-7]. In the sample, 7 carps were one-year-olds, their weight was from 72 to 120 grams, and the length was measured within 9-13 cm. The weight of a two-year-old black fish was from 128 to 136 grams, the body length was 16-17.7 cm. Three-, four- and five-year-old thrushes were also found in the samples. The body length of three-year-old thrushes was 18.1-19.8 cm, and the weight was from 142 to 144 grams. The fish brought for all samples were summarized in the specified order and included in the following table (Table 1).

Table 1

Size and age structure of black fish (*Schizotorax intermedius*) of Chervokk reservoir

Yoshi (t)	l, sm	W, gr	N
1+	9-14	72-120	7
2+	16-17,7	128-136	2
3+	18,1-19,8	142-144	3
4+	20-24,2	160-200	4
5+	25,3-28	136-164	2

Note: l – fish length; W- fish weight; n — number of samples

Black fish have 8-9 rays on dorsal fin III (usually 8), 5 rays on anal fin III; 89-95 coins on lateral line, 18 to 21 coins on upper lateral line and 15 to 19 coins below lateral line. Jabra sticks - 12-18 in first Jabra arch. Dorsal fin teeth consist of 1 to 14 pairs of well-developed teeth.

Besides that, the blackfish (*Schizothorax intermedius*) of Chervok Reservoir differs from other fish in the structure of its skin. Blackfish are distinguished by the absence of scales on the skin, the scales are of different sizes. The mouth of the blackfish has a lower or semi-lower structure, there are 2 barbels in the mouth. There are three rows of teeth in the mouth. Blackfish reach sexual maturity at the age of 3-4 years with a body length of 9.0-18.0 cm. Blackfish spawn throughout the summer. The sowing length corresponds to the length of the water level. In the Chervok Reservoir, spawning mainly occurs from April to September [9]. Blackfish spawn in the evening at a water temperature of 9-10 ° C in rocky ground. The eggs stick to the stones on the

ground, but 2-3 minutes after spawning they separate from the stones and are carried away by the current. At water temperature of 14 °C, the eggs develop in 173 hours. (Maksunov, 1968). Average density is 2700 pieces of caviar. Black fish caviar is poisonous. According to I. A. Kostina (1951), the composition of the poison begins at stage III of maturation, which coincides with the beginning of the period of large growth of caviar and increase in its size. The toxicity of caviar increases by one and a half times until it reaches stage III, and it also reaches the highest level of toxicity when the caviar reaches maximum growth after stage IV.

It is not a secret that the last component does not play a large role in the diet of black fish and may simply be unnecessary food.

Results of a study of the growth and reproduction characteristics of black fish (*Schizothorax intermedius*) of Chervok Reservoir. From fish samples taken from Chervok Reservoir, fish belonging to the carp species were isolated and their age was determined [8-9]. The growth rate was determined using measurements. Crucian carp (*Schizothorax intermedius*) is a fish species that inhabits a vast territory and is an object of local hunting in Uzbekistan. Carps are common in the mountain and foothill basins of Amudarya, Syrdarya and Zarafshan (Nikolsky, 1938; L.S. Berg, 1949; Turdakov, 1963; Amanov, 1985).

It is known that the growth of fish largely determines their viability. Such a relationship is observed throughout the life cycle of the fish. The sample of black fish we studied consisted of 19 fish specimens with a body length of 9-28 cm and a body weight of 72-264 grams. The ratio of males and females in the samples was 1:1, statistical differences between the sexes in all age groups were not found. A total of 19 carps of different sizes were delivered for sampling. To determine the age and growth rate of each, 5-6 coins were taken from the near part of the upper (dorsal) fin with special tweezers. Medicine is prepared from the coins, and the glass is fastened with medical glue so that the coins do not slip off.

Certainly, the coins were enlarged on the device "Microfort PO-5" (Chugunova's method, 1959). This device enlarges coins and displays them on the screen. Cover the screen with white paper and trace the lines of the coin rings on the screen. The age of the fish is determined by the number of rings on the gills of a black fish. Determine the central points of the rings, draw a straight line from it to the outermost ring and determine the distance from the central point to the first ring and it is equal to l_1 , and the distance from the central point to the second ring is l_2 , and the rest are written in the same order. It is measured from the central point to the outermost ring after the end of the rings and is designated in Latin by the letter S. Consider this, for example, using the example of a 4-year-old black fish.

$$l_1=7,6 \text{ sm } l_2=12,4 \text{ sm } l_3=17,1 \text{ sm } l_4=19,4 \text{ sm } W= 200 \text{ gr } l=24,2 \text{ sm } S=19,9 \text{ sm}$$

From these measurements the growth rate of the fish can be determined, and in this case there is one more measurement for us – 8.195, which is the optical measurement of the "Microfort po-5" device.

While determining the growth rate, the length of the fish, the dimensions of the mass and the distances measured from the center of the body rings are determined. l is the length of the fish; W is the weight of the fish; l_1 is the distance from the center of the ring to the end of the first ring; S is the distance from the center of the ring to the edge of the ring; 8.195 is the size of the eyepiece in this measurement.

Figure 3. An excerpt from the drawing of a four-year-old thrush on the Microfort po-5 device and the order of measuring the rings.

1- Calculation: increase the fish length l by the distance l_1 from the center of the ring on the coin to the end of the first ring.

2- Calculation: divide the obtained result by the distance from the center of the ring to the edge of the ring.

3- Calculation: divide the result obtained in the 2nd work by 8195 (this is the measurement of the eyepiece). Then the resulting number is the growth rate of the first-age fish. The growth rates of the remaining 2, 3 and 4 years are determined in the same order.

Table 2

Growth rates of carp in the Chervokk reservoir (cm)

T	l_1	l_2	l_3	l_4	l_5	n
1+	8,3					7
2+	8,5	12,4				2
3+	7,1	11,5	15,7			3
4+	7,6	12,4	17,1	19,4		5
5+	8,0	12,7	17,5	20,1	22,4	2
Average Growth increase	7,9	12,2	16,7	19,7	22,4	
	7,8	4,4	4,5	2,9	2,8	19

Note: t - ear; l - distance from the center of the ring on the coin to the end of each ring; n - number of samples.

In Chervok Reservoir, carps reach sexual maturity at the age of 2 years, and most fish reach sexual maturity at the age of 3 years. Flying schools are dominated by 3-4-year-old fish. Spawning of eggs in crucian carp is partial, spawning occurs in early April-May at a water temperature of 8-9 C. Spawning occurs mainly on sandy and rocky areas of the bottom in the upper parts of the reservoir. The eggs are large, up to 3 mm in diameter. Before spawning, the maturity level of sexual products of black fish is 9.0-15.3%. Individual absolute fecundity of fish ranges from 924 to 6390 eggs with a body length of the female of 16.5-25.0 cm. Determination of the age of black fish (*Schizothorax intermedius*) in Chervok Reservoir. Individual relative fecundity of female carp of Chervok Reservoir is also one of the variables. However, with the increase in the length and body weight of females, individual relative fertility was not observed. Analysis of the growth rates of black fish in Chervok Reservoir shows that the highest growth rate of the black

fish body corresponds to the first year of life of the fish. In the third and subsequent years of life of the fish, a significant decrease in growth rates is noted. Thus, the fastest growth of black fish in Chervok Reservoir corresponds to the first year of life of the fish, and from the second year the growth rates slow down significantly.

Firstly, this slowdown is obviously associated with the conditions of the habitat and the availability of food. Secondly, black fish reach sexual maturity at the age of 2 years, which may be associated with reproduction.

By summerising it should be suggested that based on the results, conclusions were made regarding individual absolute fertility of black fish in the reservoir which increases with age, body length and weight of the fish. Relative humidity does not increase.

REFERENCES

1. M.N Yusupova, Sh.F Irisova “Biology Of Pomegranate Pests, Control Measures And First Aid In Case Of Pesticide Poisoning” International Scientific Research Conference 2022/11/19. №1/8 P. 114-116. <https://interonconf.org/index.php/brs/article/view/246/222>
2. Makhpuza Yusupova, Shakhnoza Irisova. “Agrotechnological protection of cotton from sucking pests in various ways of planting” E3S Web of Conferences 2023 y. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202339007028>.
3. MN Yusupova, Sh F Irisova «Measures Against Grain Pests» №2/17 P.123-124. <https://interonconf.org/index.php/den/article/view/181>
4. Shakhnoza Irisova. «Protection Of Plants Sown After Cereals In The Fergana Valley» Science And Innovation International Scientific Journal Volume 2 Issue 11 November 2023 Uif-2022: 8.2 | Issn: 2181-3337 | Scientists.Uz <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10124008>.
5. Irisova Shakhnoza Fakhridinovna “The influence of seed treatment with electroactivated water before planting on the growth period of cotton”. International scientific journal "Science and innovation" Special issue: “Sustainable forestry”, November, 2023 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10084136>.
6. Alimukhamedov S.N., Kan A.A., Kozhevnikova A.G., Tukhsinov M.T., Kim-Chan-Nim. Infestation of cotton varieties and lines with sucking pests // Plant Protection. - 1995. - #2. - P. 17
7. Isaev O., Khojaev Sh. Effectiveness of "Lannet" insecticide against pests // Current affairs in cotton farming I. – practical conference. lectures. - Tashkent: , 2009. P. 300-301.
8. Irisova Sh.F. “Protection [k1] of plants sown after cereals in Fergana valley” Scientific Reports of Bukhara State University 2024/2 (107).
9. Shakhnoza Irisova. “Protection of plants sown after cereals in the fergana valley” Science And Innovation International Scientific Journal Volume 2 Issue 11 November 2023, 2022: 8.2 | Issn: 2181-3337 | Scientists.Uz <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10124008>.
10. Irisova Shakhnoza. “Bio-Ecological Features Of Blackfish (Schizothorax Intermedius) in Chervok reservoir” journal of experimental studies № 12/2023 DOI Journal 10.56017/2181-404X